

EFFECTS OF SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS ON THE SPECIFIC ENERGY
ABSORPTION OF FIBRE COMPOSITE TUBES

A. H. Fairfull and D. Hull
Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy
University of Cambridge
Cambridge
UK

ABSTRACT

The effect of the dimensions of composite components on their specific energy absorption capacity was investigated with respect to the axial crushing of cylindrical glasscloth/epoxy tubes. Compressive failure of square-ended tubes was found to be due to elastic instability or brittle fracture, depending on the dimensionless parameter t/\bar{D} . Progressive crushing was induced by chamfering one end of the tubes. Steady-state specific energy absorption increased with decreasing internal diameter and/or increasing t/\bar{D} ratio. Three crush zone configurations were identified depending on tube dimensions and resistance to ply separation. The variation of specific energy absorption with tube dimensions was plotted in the form of a design map. The action of friction was considered to be the most important topic for further work. It was concluded that there can be no universal relationship to predict energy absorption capability.

INTRODUCTION

The attractions of using fibre-reinforced plastics for automobile primary structural members are familiar, although traditionally there has been concern over the ability of these materials to "absorb" or dissipate impact energy. Using a wide variety of fibre and matrix combinations, however, Hull has shown that excellent specific energy absorption values can be obtained [1], with the high-performance composite materials offering a five-fold improvement over steel. The greatest amount of research has concerned the axisymmetric tube [1-4] chosen for ease of production by various fabrication techniques, and constant-area, edge-free cross-section. Progressive crushing can be readily initiated by an external 45° chamfer at one end. Square and rectangular section tubes have also been investigated, with alternative trigger methods proving advantageous in this case [5,6]. Specific energy absorption has been shown to be related

to the fracture toughness of the matrix material [7], and therefore varies slightly with crush speed in accordance with the strain-rate dependence of the resin properties [8].

One aspect of the crush performance of composite components of great importance to design engineers is the relationship between specific energy absorption capability and component dimensions. For example, a solid rod would not be expected to give the same force-displacement trace under long-stroke axial compression as would a thin-walled tube of the same material and cross-sectional area. This dependence on dimensions has been investigated by Fairfull [9] and Farley [10]. The work reported here concerns the crush behaviour and energy dissipation capability of cylindrical tubes fabricated from glasscloth and epoxy resin.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Tubestock was obtained from two sources. An in-house fabrication facility was developed to produce tubes from prepreg, enabling process variables to be controlled. The prepreg was Primco DV 7067 - plainwoven glasscloth impregnated with DGEBA epoxy resin - and was aligned during fabrication such that the warp and weft directions were parallel to the axial and circumferential directions of the tube. Material parameters such as volume fractions and interlaminar spacing were constant across the range of thicknesses and diameters produced. Five mandrel diameters were used, ranging from 16mm to 50mm. At least two prepreg tubes, each subsequently divided into test specimens, were fabricated to each combination of dimensions. Secondly, pre-fabricated tubes, of internal diameters of 12mm and 16mm were purchased from Tufnol Limited, under product code RLG/1. These tubes had similar glasscloth/epoxy construction to the in-house specimens.

Specimens were prepared from the tubestock by machining their end faces in a lathe. The bought-in tubes also required to be machined to the necessary wall-thicknesses. All specimens were produced with overall length $L = 3D$. The maximum possible crush load is governed by the bulk compressive strength of the material, and measurement of this required tubes with both ends faced off at 90° . Where crush initiation was required instead, one end was faced off at 90° , the other chamfered at 45° to a depth of the full wall-thickness. Figure 1 shows a typical range of prepreg specimens.

Fig.1 Range of epoxy/glasscloth specimens

All specimens were subjected to long-stroke axial compression between flat, ground steel platens at 20mm/min, using a 250kN Instron servo-hydraulic testing machine. The peak failure loads of the largest square-ended specimens were recorded on a 1000kN Dennison machine.

Fig.2 Encapsulating loaded crush zone in resin

A limited amount of information about the crush process could be obtained by visual inspection of the specimens; a more detailed analysis required microscopic examination of cross-sections taken through the crush zones. Varying degrees of elastic relaxation were observed on removal of the specimens from the testing machine, and a means was therefore devised of obtaining micrographs from specimens which were under load. The crush

zones of precrushed tubes were immersed in liquid casting resin, before reapplying the crush load (Fig.2). After curing of the casting resin, the tubes were unloaded and the required sections cut out and repotted in metallographic moulds. The sections were then polished by the standard sequence and examined at low magnification using reflected light in a Wild M8 microscope.

RESULTS

Square ended Tubes

Figure 3 shows compressive failure stress, as measured by testing square-ended prepreg tubes of 50mm internal diameter, plotted against the dimensionless parameter, t/\bar{D} . At low values of t/\bar{D} , initial failure was due to elastic instability. Peak load attainment was accompanied by the

Fig.3 Variation of failure stress with t/\bar{D}

sudden snap-in formation of irregular buckling patterns, frequently near to one end. For this failure mode, failure stress increased rapidly with increasing t/\bar{D} . In contrast, tubes of high values of wall-thickness failed by sudden brittle fracture. Most often this occurred at one end of the specimen, although several tubes fractured at a plane completely remote from the ends, the failure stress being typically slightly higher in this case. Above $t/\bar{D} = 0.05$, failure stress was independent of t/\bar{D} for all diameters of tube tested.

Chamfered Thin-walled Tubes

Subjecting chamfered prepreg tubes of 50mm internal diameter to long-stroke axial compression gave the mean crush stress versus t/\bar{D} curve shown in Fig.4. In all cases, the crosshead was stopped prior to compaction of the internal debris. The crush behaviour could be summarised as follows.

$t/\bar{D} < 0.020$. Failure involved at least some elastic buckling. Specific energy absorption increased with increasing t/\bar{D} .

$0.020 < t/\bar{D} < 0.045$. Chamfering induced progressive crushing. Specific energy absorption increased slightly with increasing t/\bar{D} .

$0.045 < t/\bar{D} < 0.085$. Chamfering induced progressive crushing. Specific energy absorption was independent of t/\bar{D} .

Fig.4 Variation of crush stress with t/\bar{D}

Chamfered Thick-walled Tubes

Figure 5 shows energy absorption data from the range of tubes shown in Fig.1, having a minimum t/\bar{D} ratio of 0.05. Clearly, specific energy absorption is not a simple material property, and is neither independent of t/\bar{D} (as might have been inferred from the results of the previous section) nor diameter alone. There was little variation with t/\bar{D} for specimens with the three larger diameters, although testing of tubes with high wall-thicknesses was limited by the 250kN capacity of the testing machine. The two sets of smaller bore specimens showed substantial variation with both internal diameter D_2 and t/\bar{D} , as shown. The 12mm and 16mm bore Tufnol specimens showed different behaviour to the prepreg tubes, as shown by the dotted curves in Fig.5. Specific energy absorption increased with increasing t/\bar{D} throughout the range of dimensions tested, $t/\bar{D} = 0.30$ representing the thickest tubes available.

Fig.5 Variation of specific energy absorption with t/\bar{D}

Microscope Studies

Although when viewed externally the travelling crush zones of all specimens appeared similar, microscopic examination of a selection of cross-sections from loaded tubes revealed substantial differences. The crush zones could be classified into three distinct configurations.

TYPE I: Long intrawall crack. Fig.6(a) represents the crush zone configuration observed in several prepreg tubes having t/\bar{D} ratios of less than 0.10. An annular wedge of tightly-compacted crush debris forces the tube wall apart causing a long Mode I crack to propagate axially along the centre-line of the wall. Normal forces from the crush platen are borne by the annular wedge and the internal and external fronds. Frictional forces resist the passage of the fronds across the platen, and the driving of the wedge into the wall. Substantial delamination occurs in the curved regions of the fronds.

TYPE II: No intrawall crack. The majority of prepreg specimens, including tubes with t/\bar{D} ratios of 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20, and all of the commercially-made tubes, exhibited this type of crush zone, shown schematically in Fig.6(b). The configuration is independent of diameter, and generalised dimensions can be quoted in terms of wall-thickness alone. There is no intrawall crack and the apex of the narrow annular wedge is positioned $0.4t$ radially from the bore of the tube. OA and OB represent the limits of delamination and are inclined as shown. Each frond deflects through a very small radius at its intersection with OA or OB, subsequent curvature within the crush zone being more gentle.

TYPE III: No crush debris deflected internally. Figure 6(c) shows the model for wholly external frond deflection, as exhibited by prepreg specimens with the highest t/\bar{D} ratios. When the chamfered region is first compressed, a solid central core of debris is formed which merges with the annular wedge, and during subsequent steady-state crushing deflects the tube wall outwards. The limit of delamination, CD, is normal to the tube axis; the fronds are therefore deflected through a much more gentle radius than in Type II, suffering less delamination damage.

The microscope studies identified two other important features of the crush zones. Firstly, the internal fronds in the Tufnol tubes inverted through a smaller radius than in the prepreg tubes. Secondly, with high wall-thickness prepreg tubes (regardless of diameter) relatively large blocks of undamaged material were prized from the outside surfaces, thus

reducing support from the debris wedge and fronds, and reducing the volume of material available for delamination.

Fig.6 Typical crush zone sections through tube wall

DISCUSSION

For steady-state crushing of any tube, there was no variation in mean crush load as crushing progressed. For tubes sufficiently short to prevent Euler buckling, specific energy absorption therefore varies only with cross-sectional dimensions. The data can thus be presented in the form of a "map" which shows the variation of failure mode with wall-thickness and diameter (Fig.7).

The shell-buckling transition is shown as $t/\bar{D} = 0.035$, based on the results from prepreg tubes of 50mm internal diameter. The transition to Type III crushing can be predicted by considering the ratio of the cross-sectional areas of internal debris and tube bore in Type II crushing as the t/\bar{D} ratio increases. Inextensional internal frond inversion becomes impossible when t/\bar{D} exceeds a critical value of 0.32. This assumes a

Fig.7 Design map for crushing of epoxy/glasscloth tubes

small radius of frond inversion, as was exhibited by the commercially made tubes. The internal fronds of the prepreg tubes, however, deflected through a larger radius, the resultant interference by diametrically opposite material causing the "premature" transition to Type III crushing observed at t/\bar{D} ratios below the critical value. Coupled with the detrimental effects of block cracking exhibited at high wall-thicknesses, this explains the drop-off in energy absorption of the small-bore prepreg tubes in Fig.5, since Type III is the least efficient of the three mechanisms.

In the Type I/Type II region of the map, specific energy absorption increased approximately linearly with t/\bar{D} , for those tubes which did not exhibit block cracking. Farley [10] found that similar relationships applied to Graphite/Epoxy and Kevlar/Epoxy tubes of $[\pm 45]_n$ configuration.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Through-thickness integrity in tubular composite specimens is vital for consistent energy absorption by axial crushing. The detachment of undamaged blocks of material must be prevented for optimum performance.

Friction within the crush zone and between specimen and platen accounts for a significant proportion of the overall level of energy dissipation. This aspect merits detailed investigation.

All of the foregoing applies specifically to the epoxy/glasscloth system. There are many other possible configurations of travelling crush zone, depending on material, lay-up and degree of through-thickness homogeneity. Whilst there may be similarities between some systems, it is clear that there can be no universal relationship to predict the "specific energy absorption of composite tubes".

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Polymer Engineering Directorate of the Science and Engineering Research Council, British Petroleum plc, Ford Motor Company Limited and Pilkington Brothers plc, and the authors are grateful for their help and encouragement.

REFERENCES

1. Hull, D., Energy absorption of composite materials under crash conditions, *ICCM IV*, 1982, pp 861-870,
2. Thornton, P.H. and Edwards, P.J., Energy absorption in composite tubes, *J. Compos. Mater.*, 16, 1982, pp 521-545.
3. Farley, G.L., Energy absorption of composite materials, *J. Compos. Mater.*, 17, 1983, pp 267-279.
4. Farley, G.L., Effect of fibre and matrix maximum strain on the energy absorption of composite materials, *J. Compos. Mater.*, 20, 1986, pp 322-334.
5. Thornton, P.H., Effect of trigger geometry on energy absorption of composite tubes, *ICCM V*, 1985, pp 1183-1199.
6. Thornton, P.H., The crush behaviour of glass fibre reinforced plastic sections, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 27, 1986, pp 199-223.
7. Keal, R., Post-failure energy absorbing mechanisms in filament wound composite tubes, PhD Thesis, University of Liverpool, 1983.
8. Berry, J.P. and Hull, D., Effect of speed on progressive crushing of epoxy-glasscloth tubes, *Inst. Phys. Conf. Ser. No. 70*, 1984, pp 463-470.
9. Fairfull, A.H., Scaling effects in the energy absorption of axially crushed composite tubes, PhD Thesis, University of Liverpool, 1986.
10. Farley, G.L., Effect of specimen geometry on the energy absorption capability of composite materials, *J. Compos. Mater.*, 20, 1986, pp 390-400.